

Synthesis of 1-Benzoyl-3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazoles and Evaluation of their Antibacterial Properties

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Manuscript received 24 May 1982, accepted 19 July 1983

ENCOURAGED by the findings of our earlier work on the study of structure-activity relationship of pyrazoles¹⁻⁵, we report the synthesis of some new azoles having the benzoyl group at position-1 in order to examine the effect of this group on the antibacterial properties and compare the results with those obtained earlier¹.

The present study deals with the synthesis and *in vitro* screening of 1-benzoyl-3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazoles of the type I.

Experimental

The different 1-aryl-3-methyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones were synthesised by coupling β -diketones with diazotised sulphonamide bases by the method reported earlier⁶.

Synthesis of 1-benzoyl-3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazoles: To a solution of 1-aryl-3-methyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)propane-1,3-dione (0.1 g) and benzoylhydrazine (0.04 g) in glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture, two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were added and the contents refluxed in a water bath for ~7 h. A coloured solid separated out on keeping the reaction mixture overnight, which was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol, glacial acetic acid-ethanol or ethanol-DMF mixture. The purity and homogeneity of these compounds was checked by m.p., elemental analysis and tlc using benzene-methanol as the solvent system. ν_{max} (KBr) 1560-1630 (C=N), 1500-1560 (N=N), 3250-3440 (NH stretching), 775-790 (S-N stretching), 1080-1090 (sym. stretching S=O), 1280-1350 (asym. stretching S=O), 1610-1615 (C=O), 720 810 (substituted phenyl).

Antibacterial activity: The results of the biological tests indicate that nearly all the pyrazole derivatives exhibit considerable activity against *S. aureus* and only a few possess very feeble activity against *E. coli*.

Contrary to our earlier observations¹ that the introduction of a phenyl ring at position-1 of the azole nucleus causes an overall decrease in activity, we find here that by inserting a carbonyl group in between the phenyl ring and nitrogen-1 of azole the activity increases. It is also observed that by introduction of benzoyl group at position-1, nearly all compounds show an increased activity against *S. aureus* compared to the pyrazoles unsubstituted at position-1. Finally, the pyrazoles having 5-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol group are found to be the most active compounds against *S. aureus*, in confirmation of our earlier results¹.

TABLE 1—1-BENZOYL-3-METHYL-5-ARYL-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYLBENZENEAZO)PYRAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C		Colour		Antibacterial activity		m.p. °C		Colour		Antibacterial activity	
		(X = Cl)	(X = Br)	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>						
1.	H	275	266	ON	BR	++	-	+	+				
2.	Acetyl	270	245	RO	O	+++	-	+	-				
3.	Phenyl	239	205	O	YO	+	-	+	+				
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	228	210	YO	R	+	-	++	-				
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	227	218	SO	OR	+	-	+	-				
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	195	227	OR	R	+	-	+	-				
7.	Guanidyl	270	270	YO	OR	+	-	+	-				
8.	α -Pyridyl	285	294	O	ON	+	-	+	-				
9.	2-Pyrimidinyl	275	> 300	YO	YO	+	-	+	-				
10.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	268	285	RO	Y	+	-	+	-				
11.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	250	250	O	Y	+	-	++	+				
12.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	295	274	RO	R	+++	-	+++	+				
13.	<i>n</i> Butylcarbamido	280	280	Y	OR	+	-	++	+				

Yield = 72 - 80%

Yield = 70 - 79%

NOTES

(contd. table 1)

		(X = CH ₃)				(X = C ₂ H ₅)			
14.	H	213	YO	+	+	245	Y	+	+
15.	Acetyl	240	O	+	+	279	YO	+	+
16.	Phenyl	212	YN	+	-	214	BO	+	+
17.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	222	R	+	+	228	R	+	+
18.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	270	O	+	-	198	BR	+	+
19.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	210	YO	+	-	221	RO	+	-
20.	Guanidyl	285	Y	+	-	255	O	+	-
21.	α -Pyridyl	270	O	+	-	250	RO	+	-
22.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	270	Y	+	-	247	R	+	-
23.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	265	YR	+	-	240	R	+	-
24.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	142	YO	+	-	217	ON	++	+
25.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	270	Y	+	+	289	Y	+++	+
26.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	260	RN	-	+	253	OR	+	+

Yield = 71-78%

Yield = 70-74%

		(X = OCH ₃)				X = OC ₂ H ₅			
27.	H	235	O	+	-	220	Y	+	-
28.	Acetyl	234	YO	+	-	275	O	+	-
29.	Phenyl	218	OR	+	-	250	YO	+	-
30.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	215	O	+	-	240	RO	+	-
31.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	BR	+	-	270	BO	+	+
32.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	130	YN	+	-	275	ON	+	-
33.	Guanidyl	292	YO	+	-	259	YO	+	-
34.	α -Pyridyl	230	O	++	-	252	RN	+	+
35.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	268	RO	+	-	225	RY	+	-
36.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	258	RN	++	+	260	OR	+	-
37.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	204	YO	++	+	275	OR	++	+
38.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	262	SR	+++	+	284	Y	+++	+
39.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	235	OR	+	-	228	YO	+	+

Yield = 71-79%

Yield = 70-78%

		(X = C ₆ H ₅)			
40.	H	277	R	+	-
41.	Acetyl	270	OR	+	-
42.	Phenyl	236	R	+	-
43.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	245	YR	+	+
44.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	155	O	++	-
45.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	232	Y	+	+
46.	Guanidyl	250	SR	+	+
47.	α -Pyridyl	245	R'	+	-
48.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	270	OR	+	-
49.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	275	YO	++	-
50.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	172	O	+	-
51.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	220	RO	+++	-
52.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	250	Y	+	-

Yield = 70-78%

B = Bright, O = Orange, R = Red, S = Shining, Y = Yellow, N = Needles.
There was good agreement between C, H found and required.

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Synthesis of a Thymol Derivative, 2-(2'-Isobutyryloxy-4-Methylphenyl)Propene from *Arnica amplexiculis*

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Manuscript received 25 October 1983, accepted 3 May 1984

THE isolation of a thymol derivative, 2-(2'-isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl)propene (III) was reported from the root extract of *Arnica amplexiculis* along with other natural products¹.